

Interactive Walkable Floor maps

**Guideline
for
teachers**

Introduction

Interactive Walkable Floor maps (IWFs) serve as educational platforms developed and tested as part of the REGREEN. It is an outcome of collaboration across research disciplines as well as across researchers, planners and teachers.

REGREEN, an EU-funded research and development project, was dedicated to advancing the implementation of Nature-Based Solutions in urban areas to tackle challenges arising from climate change and biodiversity loss.

The primary objective of IWFs is to facilitate active and interactive learning processes related to local sustainable development. Different kinds of tools and methods can be applied when working with IWFs. That is why we call it an educational platform.

This guideline aims at introducing IWFs as well as inspiring and helping schools and teachers who would like to apply IWF in their teaching.

At the end of this guideline, you can find links to further information on REGREEN, Nature-Based Solutions, technical guidance on IWF production, and related educational materials.

“It’s then up to us [the teachers] to explore this new tool with the pupils, so that they can take more conscious ownership of their living space and realise that they are an integral part of an area rich in history and resources. They need to discover it, understand it, and realise that they too can take action to help it evolve”.

Quotes from a school teacher who has been working with interactive walkable floormaps

What is an Interactive Walkable Floormap?

Imagine that you walk into large room at the school. A huge map (e.g. 4x5 meters) is laying there fixed to the floor. You can walk upon it and experience the local area in its totality. The map is based on an arial photo with a lot of details some familiar and recognizable, while others may be unfamiliar to you.

Photo: Sebastian Elze

Three ways to make floormaps interactive:

1. by teacher-participation in the process of designing the map;
2. by enabling meetings and dialogue on the map between teachers, pupils and other local agents;
3. by participatory mapping (explained on the next page)

Three reasons for applying Interactive Walkable Floormaps?

Photo: J. Læssøe

- IWFs aim at facilitating governance, participation and dialogue regarding the development of Nature-Based Solutions in urban areas. This aim does also embrace children as citizens.
- IWFs are furthermore platforms for public awareness raising and education of children. They provide a dynamic space for interactive learning.
- Moreover, IWFs can function as platforms for networking and collaboration between municipalities and schools, facilitating meaningful partnerships in the pursuit of sustainable development.

Participatory mapping on IWFs

Maps are deliberate constructs, always carrying interpretations. Participatory mapping transforms users from passive receivers to active participants. This approach aims at: 1) honing their spatial thinking, 2) fostering awareness of their surroundings, and 3) inspiring them to engage in decisions shaping the future of the area.

Interactive Walkable Floormaps facilitate participatory mapping with children. Engaging with real-world issues, the outcomes are incorporated into the floormap through QR codes, linking to discoveries, photos, field e-books, podcasts, and future visions. Additionally, contributions can be presented on transparencies that can be easily added to or removed from the floormap.

Parents, planners, and other community stakeholders are invited to experience the students' contributions and provide feedback. They can also share their own insights and perspectives. Teachers can integrate these contributions into their teaching, allowing students to learn from them and from responding to them.

Floor map of Aarhus City with contributions from children

From idea to new practices

Dall-E generated

On the one hand, your opportunities for pedagogical innovations are probably restricted. Time pressure, curricula demands, and other pressing issues, makes it difficult to adopt participatory pedagogical approaches, outdoor projects, interdisciplinary teaching etc. In REGREEN we faced this challenge in all involved countries.

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On the other hand, we saw successful ways of coping with these challenges as well. Implementation of IWF can take the point of departure in existing teaching practices and step by step introduce new elements. View examples provided on the subsequent pages

Examples from four schools

The following examples stems from our collaboration with four schools – three in Velika Gorica in Croatia and one in Argenteuil in the Paris region of France.

They are all examples of how they applied the IWF in the first months after receiving them.

Photo: J. Læssøe

Example 1: Teaching local environmental issues on the IWF

A teacher at Vukovina school outside Velika Gorica started by using the IWF to teach his pupil about the environment and the place where they are living. He guided them to observe the effects of deforestation and afforestation from a bird-eye perspective and to study places and parts of the environment that require rehabilitation interventions. His pedagogical ambition was to encourage curiosity, explorative studies, reasoning and spatial perception and thinking. As next steps, he would like to link the geographic perspective with biology and history in order to help his pupils to look at problems from multiple angles.

"You need to create an ecosystem of projects, make networks permanent, avoid the impression of imposing something, and know how to connect people by identifying their skills to create and nurture the project. For students, working with nature, help them to dream, to be curious and creative".

Quote from the teacher

Example 2: A bike project with identification of risky areas

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Two geography teachers from Nikola Hribar School in Velika Gorica collaborated to enhance a project they had done the previous year, now with the support of the IWF. They organized a competition in which their pupils utilized a mobile app to track the distance they covered while biking throughout the project period. The app also recorded their biking routes.

This year, the teachers introduced an additional task. In addition to tracking their biking activity, students were tasked with identifying areas where they felt unsafe to bike and marking those locations with stickers on the IWF.

While they initially presented the results to the pupils' parents, the teachers intend to take it a step further next year by letting their children presenting and discussing their findings with urban and traffic planners from the municipality.

Example 3: Participatory mapping with 8 grade pupils

A teacher at Eugen Kumečić School in Velika Gorica initiated an extracurricular project with eighth-grade students. The students were tasked with identifying locations in the city where they enjoy spending time and adding them to the floor map. Additionally, they were encouraged to brainstorm ideas for improving the city. Their suggestions included a hospital, kindergartens, and new sports facilities.

Subsequently, the teacher and the students engaged in discussions to determine suitable locations for these additions. Using stickers, they marked both the suggested improvements and the places they favored on the floor map. To provide clarity, they took photos of the floor map and assigned letters and numbers to the areas marked with stickers, corresponding to explanatory texts.

This project highlighted how the IWF can be employed to explore the city from a child's perspective and support their development of future orientation skills. An evident next step could involve inviting someone from the municipality to visit the IWF, offering an opportunity to respond to and discuss the students' suggestions.

8 grade students have added numbers and letters to this IWF linking to texts about places they enjoy to visit and places they want

Example 4: IWF as part of greening the school and building local identity

Photo: J. Læssøe

Presentation of the floormap for the mayor and officials from the municipality

A group of seven teachers at Pierre Brossolette school in Argenteuil/Paris integrated IWFs as part their process of greening the school. They cut transparent film into sizes, covering the areas they were interested in, and added them to the floormap. That made it possible to draw certain parts of the map on the film and to place stickers with a different colour for each of the selected themes: nature, daily life culture, art and history.

Following collaborative sessions with students on a particular theme, the educators could easily remove the film from the IWF and display it on the wall. This flexibility allowed them to revisit and augment their work, seamlessly transitioning between themes/film pieces. The students actively contributed by affixing stickers and small QR codes, each linked to photos, drawings, and texts associated with the respective themes.

In the course of these projects, the teachers fostered partnerships with municipal employees, local nature advisors, an artist, and, notably, parents. To celebrate their green initiatives, the city's mayor visited the school, dedicating over an hour to perusing the IWF transparencies and other eco-friendly projects.

Four steps

First step: Introducing the IWF and NBS

Introduce the pupils to the teaching process before they enter the floor map for the first time.

- Introduce them to what an IWF is and how it works;
- Provide them with a basic knowledge on nature based solution (NBS);
- Explain why NBS are important for their future;
- Tell them what they are supposed to do at the first walk on the map.

At the end of this guideline, you can find a list of materials containing suggestions for videos, texts and other materials that may be helpful in the introductory phase.

Illustration from 'Green-o-polis' an animated teaching material on NBS, developed as part of REGREEN

Second step: Teaching on the IWF

The first visit on the floor map can be used to:

- let the pupils take a walk on the map. Learn them to use it. Recognize what they know. Explore what they do not already know. Get an overview of the area. Get a sense of proportions. Get an impression of structures and how things are interrelated;
- introduce the legend; which signs, symbols, polygons and colors have been added by the map designers. What do they highlight?
- show examples of QR-codes and transparencies added to the map - and explain how to make them.
- show them how QR-codes can be used to link to further information about the local area and the ongoing and planned work on NBS.

Examples of questions you may ask at the first visit:

Take a walk on the map like you are flying in a helicopter over the municipality or local area:

- What are you seeing?
- Where do you live? Where is the school?
- What do you recognize?
- What do you see that you don't know what it is? Find out what it is.

Your role on the map:

- Respond to questions from the pupils;
- explain how the city and its environment has changed and introduce current plans and issues;
- highlight and expand on examples of NBS in the area covered by the IWF;
- introduce assignments on what your pupils are expected to explore by means of the IWF.

Third step: Make projects - and add them to the IWF

As mentioned earlier, IWFs are versatile platforms that can be applied with various teaching methods.

At the third level, the primary idea is to work with participatory mapping (cf. page 6) by enabling your pupils to contribute to the IWF and gain insights both from their own contributions and the feedback received.

By actively contributing to the IWF, it has the potential to evolve with data and materials reflecting, among other things:

- The pupils' unique generational perspectives on the city, its environment, and future;
- The city and its environment viewed from the perspectives of other living species;
- Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) embracing holistic sustainable development perspectives.

Depending on the grade level and discipline, or cross-disciplinary opportunities, pupils may engage in different types of contributions. Some examples are briefly described on the following pages.

Field E-books

Here the pupil's are studying their local environment by making observations, taking photos, and by using apps like 'SEEK by iNaturalist' to learn more about their findings. Afterwards they use the app 'Book Creator' to present the outcome of their study in field e-books, which are added to the IWF by means of a QR-code.

You can find a link to a detailed teacher guideline on field e-books on NBS at the last page of this guideline.

Examples of pages from Field e-books made by pupils at schools in Velika Gorica, Croatia

Citizen science projects

Originally, citizen science involved lay individuals aiding scientists in data collection, such as observing birds, amphibians, or plant species. Within the framework of REGREEN, The Nature Historic Museum in Paris has engaged schools and their pupils in citizen science projects. In this context, the objective extends beyond scientific contributions to encompass educating students about biodiversity in their local environment. Pupils acquire skills in data collection and receive valuable feedback from scientists.

The Nature Historic Museum has crafted diverse citizen science protocols and accompanying teacher guidance for schools. Some of these protocols are available in English ([link](#)).

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In your country, existing citizen science apps and databases may offer a resource for pupils. Their task could involve leveraging these databases alongside their own field studies. Moreover, citizen science projects can target urban planners within the municipality or other local entities, providing an additional avenue for pupil feedback. The IWF serves as a platform for facilitating this interactive exchange.

Local historic projects

In this particular type of project, pupils engage in the collection of photos and descriptions that illustrate the historical development of their local area. They explore questions such as: What did the area look like in the past, and what factors have contributed to its current appearance? This exploration may prompt considerations of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) within a historical context.

To compile these descriptions, pupils may conduct interviews with older residents, seeking insights into how the local environment appeared during their childhood and how it was utilized. Leveraging the resources of the local library and/or historical archive, pupils may furthermore uncover pictures and archival descriptions of the local area. These materials are then analyzed and presented using QR codes on the IWF.

Photo: J. Læssøe

Explanatory posters on local history, art and culture referring to QR-codes on the floor map transparency

GIS map projects

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IWFs can be combined with Geographic Information System (GIS) maps, which are virtual maps offering intricate details and the flexibility to modify data selections. Some municipalities provide publicly accessible GIS maps. In addition to extracting information from these maps, pupils in higher grades can acquire skills in crafting their own GIS maps. This may involve mapping daily routes, identifying attractive locations, marking spaces for specific activities, and enhancing these with personalized comments. The resulting GIS maps, enriched with the pupils' contributions, can be linked to the floor plan using QR codes.

For more in-depth information and guidance on how children can use and craft their own GIS maps, cf. 'Children, Youth and Environments', 2008, Volume 18 (2), pages 110-132.

Projects on ongoing NBS projects and plans

Through collaboration with urban planners, IWFs can be designed to showcase local Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) projects and plans. Furthermore, information related to these projects and plans can be attached to the IWF using QR codes. This collaborative approach can help you and your students to identify and select specific areas for in-depth studies.

By visiting these chosen locations, you and your pupils gain firsthand insights into the NBS projects. You may then let your pupils assess these NBS projects through the lenses of nature and child perspectives. Moreover, pupils have the opportunity to formulate their own suggestions for changes or improvements to them. These suggestions can be shared and published on the floor plan through the use of QR codes, creating a dynamic platform for interactive engagement.

This floormap has been added lines and polygons showing areas with NBS or plans for NBS

Future workshops

The school may organize workshops, inspired by the future workshop method, where your pupils create visions and consider opportunities for development of NBS in their local area.

As an outset, NBS and the future workshop phases are introduced. Next critical issues are identified. During the visionary phase, students unleash their imagination, envisioning the future of their local area and contemplating the impact of realizing their NBS visions on their daily lives. Following this, the workshop transitions into the 'realization phase.' Here, students compare their visions with the municipality's NBS plans for the same area. They meticulously evaluate the merits and potential risks of both their own visions and the existing municipal plans.

The workshop's outcomes are then processed and communicated using QR links on the floor map

Illustration generated by Dall-E

Forth step: Dialogue with people outside the school

IWFs may be applied as a dynamic platform for dialogue between pupils and individuals beyond the school community. Pupils enhance their learning outcome by presenting their contributions on the IWF to specially invited external guests. In this interactive setting, they not only share their insights but also glean valuable knowledge from the feedback from the invited guests as well as from engaging in discussions with them about Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and the future of their local area.

Considerations for potential 'outsiders' to invite for visits and discussions may include parents, local residents, members of non-governmental organizations (NGOs), experts from various fields such as nature advisors, professionals from public administration, and even local politicians. This diverse mix of participants enriches the dialogue, providing pupils with a broad perspective on their ideas and fostering meaningful connections between the school and the wider community.

The IVAC didactical model made by Bjarne Bruun Jensen:

I = investigate, V= visioning, A= act, C= change: The pupils are *investigating* a selected area, then develop *visions* for it, *act* to make their visions real and learn from being confronted with other citizens and decision makers during their efforts to *change* the selected area.

This approach has been disseminated by UNESCO and used at several hundred places as part of '*Sandwatch*'. For further inspiration, take a look at www.sandwatch.org

Three levels of ambition

School Class Level: Each pupil, individually or in groups, contributes observations or narratives to the IWF, collectively forming a multi-narrative focused on a specific area.

School Level: Groups of pupils collaborate to contribute to the creation of a comprehensive local IWF addressing one or more specific issues within the school.

Inter-School Level: Multiple schools contribute to a shared public municipality map, a collaborative effort that extends to city planners participating in this collective endeavor.

Images generated by Dall-E

Supportive materials

- Technical guideline: How to design and produce Interactive Walkable Floormaps: [How to Design Interactive Walkable Floor Maps - IWF - \(zenodo.org\)](#)
- Teacher guideline on Nature-based Solutions: [link will be added asap]
- Teacher guideline on how to make field e-books: [link will be added asap]
- Greenopolis: Animated teaching material on Nature-based Solutions: <https://greenopolis.regreen-project.eu/>
- Vigie nature ecole citizen science for schools: <https://www.vigienature-ecole.fr/en/node/15>

Background information

REGREEN in brief

Funded by the European Union in 2019, REGREEN's 24 partners have since been collaborating across cities, countries, academic disciplines and across research and urban planning to foster "nature-based solutions for equitable, green and healthy urban transitions in Europe and China" (<https://www.regreen-project.eu/>).

Nature-based Solutions (NBS)

Nature-based solutions (NBS) are solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience. Such solutions bring more, and more diverse, nature and natural features and processes into cities, landscapes and seascapes, through locally adapted, resource-efficient and systemic interventions.

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